

**WASTE MANAGEMENT AGENCY PRACTICES IN UYO METROPOLIS:
ANALYSIS OF AKWA IBOM STATE ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION AND
WASTE MANAGEMENT AGENCY (AKSEPWMA) AKWA IBOM STATE,
NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

Waste management and control is one of the major problems that urban centres are facing in Nigeria. Globally, human population has grown rapidly as a result of industrialization hence the migration of people from rural areas to the urban centres or cities. This situation have put severe pressure on the environment which has led to increase of wastes among the city dwellers. This paper present a case study conducted in Uyo Capital City of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria on the impact of waste management and disposal practices. A total of 100 households from the (5) major roads in Uyo capital city were selected for the study using purposive sampling procedure. Findings from the study revealed that the common waste disposal practices in Uyo capital city were; drive and throw, burning, littering and very few took their waste to public disposal facilities in their vicinity. Some of the respondents have their personal waste bin in their homes/shops in the study area, but it took them a week or more to dispose the refuse despite the quantity. It is recommended that officers of the Akwa Ibom State Environmental Protection and Waste Agency (AKEPWMA) is responsible for waste collection and evacuation in Uyo, they must make it mandatory for every household in Uyo capital city to have at least one waste bin or basket in their houses as a way of preventing littering of wastes that could block drainages which may likely leads to flooding in the city.

KEYWORDS: Waste Management, Disposal Practices, Pollution, Health

INTRODUCTION

Environmental issue in Akwa Ibom State was one of the most neglected issues of discussion, but now it is one of such issues that is occupying the centre stage of the local and international fora (Akpan and Ahmed, 2011). Nigerian cities in recent time have witnessed unprecedented rise in urban growth resulting from influx of migrants from rural areas to the cities. Thus, as the population of the city grows, the tons of waste generated also increases leading to increase burning of refuse and high rate of air pollution which increases concentration of greenhouse gases that causes global warming and eventually climate change. In Uyo, Akwa Ibom State and Nigeria in general, the frequently practiced waste disposal methods are open dumping, open-air burning and waste burial, which are not only unsatisfactory but also unfavourable to public health (Omole, *et al*, 2016).

Waste management practices differ from country to country depending on the waste sources, types and characteristics. It plays a vital role in nature's ability to sustain life within its capability. In many developing countries of the world, it has become a recurrent challenge, especially in urban areas. Waste generation in Uyo capital city is on the increase due to the rise in population resulting from the techno-economic development in cities and the pattern of production and consumption of materials. The current waste management practices in the state capital are fast becoming a state issue and unsustainable, leading to apparent environmental risk and enforcement of environment regulations and laws, as posited by Aguoru and Alu (2015) that considerable percentage of urban waste in developing countries is deposited either on the roadsides, unapproved dumpsites, drainage system, or in open sites which adversely affect environmental friendliness.

However, indiscriminate waste disposal practices are not environmentally friendly, because waste emits offensive odour (air pollution), favours the breeding of rodents that can cause malaria, lassa fever, flies, harmful reptiles and other vectors that has some poisoning effects on humans. It has been observed that indiscriminate waste disposal practices destroys the aesthetics value of the city. Above all, Nation Environmental Health Practice Regulations (2016) Part III states that “no person shall disposed of any waste whether solid or liquid in any place except as approved by the environmental health authority responsible for the area”. On this backdrop, this paper seeks to collect and analysis information on the perception of the people on the waste management practices of Akwa Ibom State Environmental Protection and Waste Management Agency (AKSEPWMA).

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

This paper appraised waste management in Uyo Akwa Ibom State Nigeria with a view to both identifying the existing waste management and disposal practices. The paper had identified the current challenges facing waste management to include poor funding, poor collection techniques, grossly inadequate collection equipment, reckless disposal of waste in our environment, huge increase in population and urbanization, lack of trained professional waste managers. The problem of waste management has posted a serious threat to our environment making it unhealthy to humans, it has become a debilitating factor towards sustainable development in Uyo Capital City. In the light of these challenges, the paper advocates for proper waste management, increased funding for the management of waste and commitment from government. It is on the above background that this paper is set to examine

activities of Akwa Ibom State Environmental Protection and Waste Management Agency (AKSEPWMA) within Uyo metropolis in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Environmental issues in Nigeria is now the top most priority of every successive administration in the country aim at having a healthy environment. Thus, as the population of the city grows, the tons of waste generation also increases leading to increase in burning of refuse and high rate of air pollution. The release of toxic waste into the environment is worrisome because of its health effect. Aside, the environmental impact of the pollution or contamination of soils, their physical and mechanical properties can get altered. Soil contamination is caused by tons of chemical waste deposited underground arises from variety of sources, which include acid rain, improper waste disposal among others (Omole, 2016).

Effective waste management all depends on effective regulations and policy guidelines of environmental sustainability. These regulations show how Akwa Ibom State is committed to sustainable and efficient management of the environment. There exist several agencies and laws that regulate waste management in Akwa Ibom State. These include the State Ministry of Environment, the National Environmental Standards Regulatory and Enforcement Agency (NESREA) Act of 2007. The Act confirm regulations and protection of natural resources in the environment for sustainable development.

Conceptual Clarification

Waste management agency are the organize body responsible for evacuation of waste in Uyo Capital City (Peter, 2022).

Waste Disposal: According to Britannica (2018), waste disposal refers to the collection, processing and recycling or deposition of the waste materials from human society. The term “Waste” covers both solid wastes (refuse or garbage) and sewage.

Types of Waste

Waste comes in different forms and may be categorized in a variety of ways. The types listed in this study are no necessarily exclusive and there may be considerable overlap so that one waste entity may fall into types.

- i. **Liquid Waste:** Liquid waste is commonly found both in households as well as in companies. This waste includes dirty water, organic liquids, waste detergents and waste chemical water.
- ii. **Solid Waste:** Solid waste can include a variety of items found in our households along with commercial and industrial locations. Solid waste are commonly broken down into the following types:
 - **Plastic Waste:** This consists of bags, containers, jars, bottles and many other products that can be found in our households.
 - Plastic is not bio-degradable, but many types of plastic can be recycled.
 - **Paper/Card Waste:** This includes packaging materials, newspapers, cardboards and other paper products.
 - **Tins and metals:** This can be found in various form throughout our homes. Most metals can be recycled.

- **Ceramic and glass:** These items can easily be recycled.
- iii. **Organic Waste:** Organic waste is another common household waste. All food waste, manure and rotten meats are all classified as organic waste. Over time, organic waste is turned into manure by micro-organisms. However, this does not mean that we cannot dispose them anywhere.
- iv. **Recyclable Waste:** Recyclable waste include all waste items that can be converted into products which can be used again. Solid items such as papers, plastics, metals, furniture and organic waste can be used again. Solid items such as papers, plastics, metals, furniture and organic waste can all be recycled.
- v. **Hazardous Waste:** Hazardous waste include all types of waste that are flammable, toxic, corrosive and reactive. These items can harm human beings as well as the environment and must be disposed of correctly.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In this study, the Human Ecological Theory of Robert E. Park (1864-1944) was adopted to offer explanations to the issue of Waste Management and Disposal Practices in Uyo Capital City, Akwa Ibom State. Human Ecological Theory was developed by Robert Ezra Park in Chicago School. Park was an American urban sociologist. He coined the concept of Human Ecology as a perspective that attempts to apply biological processes and concepts to the social world. Park maintained that the city and life in the city is a product of competition in the natural environment.

Human ecological theory embodies the idea that human beings influence the natural environment in their cities positively or negatively due to their activities in the environment. The theory centres in human behaviours and their impact on the natural environment. The study of human behaviour as an integrated social and ecological phenomenon shows a strong evidence on the influence of human on the natural environment through waste disposal practices like open dumping, open-air burning and waste burial, which are not only unsatisfactory, but also unfavourable to public health (Omole *et al.*, 2016).

The ecological approach examines a variety of variables such as the urban environment itself. Park's theory may have not been concise and clear in its findings as purported by critics, but it has certainly paved the way for modern sociology and for the future of sociology. This theory has proven beyond reasonable doubt that truly human beings are the problem of most environmental issues that causes a great danger to the city life. Waste can be categorized according to its physical form, source and environmental impact. It can be solid, liquid or gas and come from sources like households, industries, agriculture, commercial sites and so on (Petar *et al.*, 2022).

Aguroru and Alu (2015) posited that considerable tons of urban waste in developing countries are deposited on roadsides or unapproved dump sites, in water ways that blocks damages which adversely affect our environment by destroying and also poses serious health challenges such as dysentery, cholera and malaria all these are problems caused by human activities in the environment which is harmful to the environment and human beings.

METHODOLOGY

A survey research design was adopted for the study toward achieving the research

objectives. Uyo metropolis is a growing state capital in modern Nigeria. The city has over some years now experienced increase in population which has led to expansion of the state capital. Stratified random sampling was adopted by the researchers for interview and data collection. Uyo metropolis was stratified by major roads which form the strata and households form the stratum for the study. A total of 100 households from the (5) major roads including Aka road, Ikot Ekpene road, Oron road, Abak road, and Nwaniba road within Uyo capital city were purposively selected for the study. Households were randomly selected with each road having a selection of 5 household each with random selection which gives every household the chance to be part of the study. Interview schedule was developed by the researchers for the data through interview which enabled the collection of first-hand information from the study participants. Data was analysed thematically with excerpts from the study participants.

RESULT

Study participants across various roads in Uyo metropolis in their responses, the majority of the study commended the efforts of the Akwa Ibom State Environmental Protection and Waste Management Agency (AKSEPWMA) in prompt evacuation of waste.

In an interview with one Mr. Felix Edem, a landlord in Idoro road, Uyo. He said that;

I am happy with the management of (AKSEPWMA) because over the years they were unable to evacuate waste frequently and this brought about air pollution in the area. He said that the waste management agency now employed enough supervisors who monitor all the dump site and ensure that waste are evacuated on time (interviewed on 20-3-2024).

In an interview with a cross section of traders in Iram market, the study participants also commended the efforts of the waste management agency chaired by Prince Ikim. One of the participants reported that;

I thank the agency for ensuring that all the drainage are properly clean-up in order to allow erosion to flow. I am grateful for their works and how the agency are evacuating waste on daily basis that they are enjoying proper hygiene, (interviewed on 21-3-2024).

In an interview with 100 household selected across major roads in Uyo metropolis, the study participants in their responses reported that they are happy with the waste management agency for prompt evacuation of waste and maintaining the aesthetic value of the city and solicited more funding for the agency. According to a participant;

The waste management people have been trying seriously in Uyo. They always try to come and pack the waste every two days and that has make the market environment very clean (trader, interviewed on 21-3-2024).

In an interview with a cross section of traders in Akpan Andem market, the traders were happy with the management of waste

management agency for ensuring that waste evacuation is done on daily basis. The traders caution themselves that they should ensure that waste are dump properly inside the receptacle for proper sanitation.

The researcher observed that Uyo metropolis is very clean now because of the seriousness in waste evacuation by the workers of waste management agency. The researcher observed that their evacuation trucks were moving across various dump sites in the street of Uyo to ensure that waste were properly evacuated.

In an interview with one of the staff of (AKSEPWMA) who gave his name as Mr. David Daniel, he said that all their staff are happy with the management for increasing the salaries and also giving them hazard allowance to use and treat themselves. Other respondents thank the chairman of waste management agency Prince Ikim for introducing end of the year and new year packages where items like bags of rice, oil, tomato and cash donations are given to them as encouragement.

Findings of the study through gathered data have shown that Akwa Ibom State Environmental Protection and Waste Management Agency (AKSEPWMA) has been up to date in combating indiscriminate waste disposal within Uyo metropolis.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings have shown that in Itam industrial layout and Itam market areas, there was a private arrangement for evacuation of waste with the use of wheel barrows and cart pushers who would from time to time come to the aid of the traders and motor parks indisposing their wastes in the approved dump site as shown in figure 2. It was shown that in most strategic approved locations, waste evacuation were handle by the Akwa Ibom State Environmental Protection and Waste Management Agency (AKSEPWMA) as shown in figure 1. It was also revealed that the agency were able to evacuate waste frequently as shown in figure 3 in the appendix, and there was no air pollution in the environment.

The study revealed that most homes were disposing their waste through “burning”. It was also revealed that some households were operating waste burial, which is unfavourable to public health. While others were practicing open dumping of waste. This could explain the reason why some of the households did not have waste containers because their waste is either burnt, buried or littered in any open space. Many respondents said that they use to dispose their waste with polythene bags. This accounts for dumping of refuse in water ways, drainages and roadsides.

Findings from the study also revealed that respondents who said that they have been sorting their waste did not have waste containers. As such, it is not clear and unrealistic for one to sort waste without having it in a waste basket or container. The respondents seemed to know that it helps to sort waste, but only few were practicing it.

The evacuation of waste in Uyo Capital City is said to be the duty of the Akwa Ibom

State Environmental protection and waste management agency (AKSEPWMA). The study revealed the main challenges of waste management agency to include poor funding, insufficient evacuation trucks, in sufficient number of receptacles at the approved dumping site along the roadside. The study affirm that the flooding problem experienced in Uyo Capital City is as a result of dumping of refuse in drainages.

The study revealed that indiscriminate disposal of waste emits offensive odour (air pollution), it also provide breeding space for rodents, mosquitoes, flies, harmful reptiles and other vectors that have some poisoning effects on humans.

From the findings of this study, it was found that not all areas in Uyo Capital City enjoy effective waste collection services due to lack of adequate prompt waste evacuation and truck breakdown. It was revealed that most of these hired trucks have been overused. A staff of Akwa Ibom State Environment Protection and Waste Management Agency (AKSEPWMA) acknowledge that the agency has enough workers and enough evacuation trucks. He said that their workers were well paid and also given hazard allowance. He said that the management are treating them well and that is why they have been able to clear all the dump sites that was seen by the public as eyesore.

CONCLUSION

Waste management and disposal practices is crucial not just for environmental protection, but also as a source of life livelihood. To attain an effective and efficient waste collection system requires that proper framework that is well designed and enforced. The current study provides evidence that a stable government with a firm commitment to waste management fundamental. The policy direction suggested here is to revise current regulations and laws, create public awareness through rampant public education programmes, then support the laws and regulations through string enforcement measures. More importantly, the entire waste management system calls for total cooperation between government, private sectors and humanitarian organizations. Finally, a successful implementation of waste management techniques will protect our environment and eradicate some of the deadliest diseases in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. The government of Akwa Ibom State should activate the waste recycling company in Uyo in other to encourage proper evacuation of waste in Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. The environmental health officers in partnership with the law enforcement agents should be ready to arrest and prosecute any offender of the environmental laws of the state.
- iii. Government should sensitized the residents on the approved dump sides, and the stipulated time to dump their wastes.
- iv. Government should provide the Akwa Ibom State Environmental Protection and Waste Management Agency (AKSEPWMA) with new evacuation trucks and pay loaders for prompt waste disposal.

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